

Skills 4 eosc

D8.5 Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan - final version

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable presents the final outcomes of Skills4EOSC dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities, led by Work Package 8. Through extensive outreach and stakeholder engagement, the project advanced a European approach to Open Science training, promoting Minimum Viable Skillsets, a data stewardship curriculum, and collaboration via Competence Centres. Communication efforts, including social media, events, and user-friendly materials, effectively reached diverse stakeholders, raised awareness of project outputs, and supported alignment with European Open Science policies. The establishment of the Competence Centres Network underpins the long-term sustainability of project impacts, ensuring continued capacity-building and integration into the EOSC landscape.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CC	Competence Centre
CCs	Competence Centres
Comms	Communications
D&E&C	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A	European Open Science Cloud Association
EUA	European University Association
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
Knowledge Broker	One of the actors at the Science for Policy interface, acting as impartial mediator between science and policy actors.
LERU	League of European Research Universities
MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset

OS	Open Science
OSRI	Open Science Ready Institution
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
RRI	Responsible Research & Innovation
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
TtT	Train the Trainers
UNITE!	University Network for Innovation, Technology and Engineering
VRT	Virtual Round Table

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1 Executive Summary

Over the past three years, Work Package 8 (WP8) "Synergies, stakeholder engagement, advocacy" has led the project's outreach efforts across all levels. In particular, Task 8.6 "Communications and outreach" worked in close collaboration with the other Work Packages, maintaining an ongoing dialogue to effectively reach stakeholders and foster their engagement throughout the project lifecycle. This was essential to ensure that the objectives and impacts of Skills4EOSC were successfully achieved.

This deliverable outlines the final outcomes of the dissemination, exploitation, and communication (D&E&C) efforts, focusing on the strategies, tools, and channels used to reach stakeholders, foster engagement, and communicate the project's key results. Building on previous deliverables (D8.3 and D8.4), this report highlights the ongoing activities and evaluates the effectiveness of the communication channels, the implementation of the dissemination strategy, and the long-term sustainability of the project's outputs.

The Skills4EOSC project has significantly impacted the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) landscape, contributing to the development of Open Science skills, policies, and infrastructures. The project's core activities centred around creating a unified, European approach to Open Science training and capacity-building, facilitating the widespread adoption of Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS), developing a European curriculum for data stewardship, and fostering collaboration through national and international Competence Centres.

As the project progressed, extensive outreach and communication efforts were employed, utilizing a wide range of media and tools, from social media and project websites to webinars and conferences. These efforts not only communicated the project's deliverables but also promoted a shared understanding of Open Science across a broad spectrum of stakeholders, from research professionals and institutions to policy makers and public sector actors.

Key dissemination initiatives included the development of visually cohesive deliverables, the launch of a Booklet Series that translated complex project outputs into user-friendly materials, and a variety of events, workshops, and webinars that enhanced the visibility of the project. In addition, the project's communication strategy targeted national, pan-European, and international stakeholders, ensuring that the results reached the right audiences at the right time.

The project also made significant strides in aligning its work with key European Open Science initiatives and policies, directly contributing to the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) and collaborating with other related initiatives. The establishment of the Competence Centres Network has played a critical role in the long-term sustainability of the Skills4EOSC project, ensuring continued knowledge exchange, resource sharing, and capacity-building across Europe.

Looking ahead, the dissemination and exploitation efforts initiated by Skills4EOSC are expected to have a lasting impact on the development of Open Science skills, both within the research community and beyond, through the continued engagement of Competence Centres and the broader EOSC ecosystem.

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose of the document

WP8 is responsible for ensuring synergies, stakeholder engagement, and advocacy, with a strong focus on dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities to promote the project's actions and results to key target stakeholders.

The impact achieved through the wide range of activities implemented has been significant. Dissemination efforts have reached stakeholders, organisations, and individuals across Europe — and beyond — in a widespread and effective manner.

Given the Skills4EOSC overall activities, dissemination and engagement efforts have particularly focused on the key exploitable results (KERs) of the project, including:

- Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS) for OS-related profiles;
- A European curriculum for data stewards;
- FAIR-by-design methodology for training materials;
- Professional networks and user support structures;
- Course designs and resource kits for trainers and policy engagement.

The communication strategy targeted a broad spectrum of audiences, from science professionals and academia to the public sector and EOSC/OS stakeholders, tailoring messages and channels to each. Despite limited resources, the project maximised impact by leveraging the diversity and motivation of partners. Priority was given to national and pan-European engagement, ensuring wide dissemination and fostering adoption of project outputs. Through the network of Competence Centres and collaboration with EOSC-related initiatives, we have strengthened visibility, engagement, and sustainability pathways for Skills4EOSC results.

This deliverable provides a detailed summary of the project's final year D&E&C activities, showcases the tools and channels used to engage with stakeholders, and outlines the achievements and ongoing efforts to ensure

the sustainability of the project’s results. Through these activities, Skills4EOSC has laid a strong foundation for the future development of Open Science training and capacity-building across Europe.

2.2 Structure of the document

This deliverable is structured to provide a comprehensive overview of the dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities carried out throughout the Skills4EOSC project.

Following the **Introduction**, **Section 2** presents a mapping of stakeholders and target audiences.

Section 3 outlines the key results of D&E&C efforts during Year 3, highlighting visual identity improvements, support tools, and engagement strategies.

Section 4 details the communication and dissemination activities, including online channels, event participation, and promotional materials.

Finally, **Section 5** focuses on the exploitation and sustainability strategy, including co-creation methodologies, national use cases, and the Competence Centres Network.

2.3 Mapping of stakeholders and target audiences

The communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy of Skills4EOSC is rooted in the recognition of a highly diverse stakeholder landscape. In order to maximise relevance and impact, the project has defined five macro-level target groups, each representing a distinct set of needs, roles and potential for uptake of Skills4EOSC results. These groups encompass professionals involved in research, education, governance, and infrastructure development, both within and beyond the EOSC framework.

1. Science Professionals

This category brings together the individuals who are most directly involved in conducting, supporting or enabling research. It includes:

- Researchers at all stages of their careers, from PhD candidates to senior scientists;

- Domain-specific or sectoral experts contributing subject knowledge;
- Data stewards and data managers responsible for the research data lifecycle;
- Legal and ethical advisors supporting responsible research practices;
- Research support staff offering administrative and technical services;
- Professional trainers delivering skills development within institutions.

These stakeholders have been primary users of training curricula, Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS), and FAIR-by-Design resources. Skills4EOSC empowered them with tools and guidance to adopt Open Science practices in a consistent and sustainable way.

2. Public Sector Stakeholders

The public sector has a dual role: as both enabler and beneficiary of Open Science. Skills4EOSC engaged with a variety of actors who influence science policy and funding, manage open data infrastructures, or seek to improve public decision-making through evidence-informed processes. These include:

- Civil servants and public administration representatives;
- Policymakers and decision-makers in ministries, research institutions, and governmental bodies;
- National and regional funding agencies and research councils;
- Regulatory bodies and programme management agencies.

By adopting Open Science and FAIR data approaches, these actors can contribute to policy alignment, ensure long-term sustainability of research investments, and promote responsible innovation.

3. Academia and Research Organisations

This group includes the institutional backbone of the European Research Area: organisations that produce knowledge, train future professionals, and participate in standard-setting. It covers:

- Public and private Research Performing Organisations (RPOs);
- Universities and their departments, schools and libraries;
- National and international Research Infrastructures (RIs);
- National rector conferences and associations;

- Umbrella organisations (e.g. ScienceEurope) promoting shared research standards.

Skills4EOSC engaged with these actors through training pilots, co-creation of curricula, and capacity-building for Competence Centres, helping to embed Open Science into institutional strategies and daily practice.

4. Open Science and EOSC Actors

A final, crucial audience consists of those actively shaping the EOSC ecosystem. These actors are not only key allies in ensuring uptake of Skills4EOSC outputs, but also important multipliers and co-creators. They include:

- EOSC Association and its working groups and task forces;
- EOSC Steering Board and national contact points;
- National Open Science initiatives and mandated organisations;
- EOSC-related projects, infrastructures and technical platforms;
- International networks such as OpenAIRE, RDA, GO FAIR Foundation.

Engaging these stakeholders helped ensure alignment with evolving EOSC policies and standards, enabling Skills4EOSC to contribute directly to the implementation of the European Open Science Cloud and the future European Skills Academy.

3 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication key results in Year 3

3.1 Harmonising visual identity and optimising deliverables presentation

In 2025, the Skills4EOSC consortium implemented an updated set of graphical and editorial guidelines aimed at enhancing the clarity, reusability and visual coherence of project deliverables. These “Guidelines for Optimising Skills4EOSC Deliverables” (v1.1, March 2025) were developed in response to the need to better align communication outputs with the project’s strategic positioning and to increase the impact and recognisability of its results across multiple stakeholder groups.

The guidelines serve both as a practical tool and a quality benchmark for all contributors producing public-facing documents. Their purpose is twofold: first, to improve the usability of deliverables by end-users such as researchers, trainers, policy stakeholders and data stewards; and second, to establish a shared visual and editorial identity that strengthens the Skills4EOSC brand within the broader EOSC ecosystem.

Key improvements introduced include:

- **Standardised deliverable structure**, promoting logical organisation of content, inclusion of quick-start guides, summaries of key concepts, and clearly defined target audiences.
- **Simplified and accessible language**, with recommendations for short sentences, limited jargon, and explanatory glossaries to ensure comprehension by non-experts.
- **Enhanced visual elements**, such as flowcharts, checklists, templates, and infographics. Dedicated icons and diagram sets were provided to reinforce recognisability and usability across areas of action (e.g., training, policy, FAIR-by-design).
- **Thematic colour coding**: each project area (e.g., Minimum Viable Skillsets, Competence Centres, Training of Trainers, Policy support) is associated

with a dedicated colour, facilitating immediate visual identification and alignment across media (documents, presentations, web content).

- **Accessible and inclusive formatting**, including screen-reader-compatible PDFs, high-contrast colour schemes, and recommendations to reduce reliance on complex tables and dense text layouts.
- **Dedicated templates** for Word, OnlyOffice and presentation slides, available to all partners, ensure visual consistency and reduce production time while improving professional appearance.
- **Consistent logo usage** with multiple configurations (positive/negative, with or without payoff), adapted to various formats and backgrounds, supported by a clear visual do/don't guide.

By adopting these guidelines, Skills4EOSC significantly improved the coherence and effectiveness of its communication strategy. The unified visual language has not only increased the visibility of deliverables—especially when disseminated via social media or presented at events—but also improved stakeholder trust and engagement. Outputs such as the *Science4Policy Kit*, the *Competence Centre Roadmap*, and the *FAIR-by-Design methodology* benefitted from this harmonisation, making them more attractive, easier to navigate, and more likely to be adopted and reused by external audiences.

The guidelines also include a forward-looking section on updates and feedback, encouraging contributors to continuously refine their documents based on stakeholder input. This participatory and iterative approach ensures that the quality and usability of project materials continue to improve over time, supporting long-term exploitation and sustainability of Skills4EOSC results.

Skills4EOSC Guidelines and Visual Identity

3.2 Promoting project initiatives and outputs

3.2.1 Skills4EOSC Booklets Series

As part of its broader communication and exploitation strategy, Skills4EOSC launched a dedicated **Booklet Series** to enhance the visibility and usability of its most strategic outputs. This initiative aims to turn selected project deliverables into concise, visually engaging publications tailored to a wide array of stakeholders, from policy actors to trainers, research professionals and institutional managers.

Rather than merely summarising technical documents, the booklet format reinterprets content through a design-first lens: short texts, rich graphics, colour-coded thematic areas, and actionable messages make each booklet a stand-alone product, optimised for dissemination, training sessions, and institutional engagement. All booklets are openly available via the project website and Zenodo, ensuring persistent access and reuse.

As of July 2025, the Booklet Series includes the following titles:

- **The Building Blocks of a Data Steward Training Curriculum:** outlining the key components, structure and modular logic behind a robust, reusable European data stewardship curriculum.
- **Starter Kits for Professional Networks – Data Steward Creators:** a concise handbook guiding the formation and growth of data steward communities within the Competence Centre Network.
- **Guidelines and FAQs on ELSI Aspects for Civil Servants and Policy Makers:** a tailored resource offering clear explanations and frequently asked questions on ethical, legal and social implications.
- **Science4Policy Kit for Competence Centres:** a toolkit featuring ten real-world case studies to assist centres in bridging science and policymaking.
- **Minimum Viable Skillsets: A Briefing for Competence Centres:** an overview of the MVS methodology, designed to clarify essential roles in Open Science.
- **Data Steward: Minimum Viable Skills Profile:** a role-specific profile detailing two archetypes—coordinator and embedded data stewards.

- **Guidelines and Best Practices for Honest Brokers:** advice aimed at individuals who facilitate unbiased evidence delivery to policy contexts.
- **FAIR-by-Design Methodology for Learning Materials:** a booklet laying out the methodology that ensures educational materials are reusable, interoperable and high quality.
- **Advancing Evidence-Based Policymaking through Open Collections and Open Science Principles:** a policy-focused booklet linking Open Science practices to the realisation of UN Sustainable Development Goals.
- **How to Write a Privacy Policy in a Research Project:** a practical template and guide for drafting compliant privacy documents in research settings.
- **Catalogue of MVS Profiles** – an updated version of the Data Steward Minimum Viable Skills Profile, expanded as a comprehensive directory of professional profiles.
- **S4E Quality Compass** – a booklet designed to guide trainers and centres in evaluating the robustness and quality of their training provision.
- **Top 10 FAIR Data Things for AI** – a concise guide outlining the most critical FAIR data principles for AI practitioners and organisations.

Each booklet presents information using consistent visual branding (colour-coded themes, icons, infographics and user-friendly layouts) ensuring they are both visually cohesive and easy to navigate. Moreover, their compact size makes them ideal for targeted dissemination within national Competence Centres, at conferences, and via social media, maximising outreach beyond academic audiences.

Together, the Booklet Series exemplifies Skills4EOSC commitment to crafting outputs that are not only rigorous and professional, but also creatively packaged for widespread understanding, reuse and impact.

Skills4EOsc Booklet Series

3.3 Supporting work packages and partners in outreach

3.3.1 Virtual Round Tables

Virtual Round Tables (VRTs) are structured discussion sessions designed to support strategic alignment, mutual understanding, and cross-cutting collaboration among consortium partners. Organised within WP1 ‘Project management’, they go beyond regular project meetings by providing a dedicated space for reflection, knowledge exchange, and the identification of gaps or emerging needs across work packages.

Each VRT focused on a central theme, introduced through short presentations, followed by an open, moderated discussion. All consortium members were represented, with active involvement from task leaders and contributors. The sessions proved to be a valuable tool to enhance internal communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts by aligning perspectives, surfacing insights, and strengthening collective ownership of project directions and results.

The topics discussed were:

- Sustainable development and community building (March 2023), focusing on long-term vision, post-project sustainability, and the adaptation of Competence Centres (CCs) to regional contexts.
- Definitions of Open Science (June 2023), aiming at a shared, yet flexible, understanding of Open Science across disciplines, with emphasis on practical actions and policy relevance.
- Impact of the new EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR) 2025–2027 (January 2024), addressing strategic alignment with emerging EOSC policy priorities in training, skills development, and research careers.

The VRTs effectively fostered partner engagement, encouraged bottom-up feedback, and supported community building. They also contributed to extending the consortium’s collective capacity beyond the immediate project objectives—positioning the VRT format as a replicable practice for strategic internal alignment in complex, multi-partner initiatives.

3.3.2 Internal Newsletters

Since January 2024 and on quarterly basis, an internal newsletter was created and disseminated within Skills4EOSC partners by email. The purpose of the newsletter was to widely circulate relevant actions, news, collaborations and important milestones of the project to all project participants. The internal newsletter was utilized as a complimentary channel to the project website, as well as the consortium’s plenary meetings, for ensuring that all partners were informed with the same accurate and spherical information.

Every three months, WP leaders were asked to provide their contributions in order to be used as input for the creation of the current newsletter. All the material, as well as the issues created so far are publicly available in the common workplace, in the dedicated folder “Internal newsletter”.

3.4 Positioning in the EOSC ecosystem and alignment with policy priorities

The Skills4EOSC project played a pivotal role within the European Open Science Cloud ecosystem by addressing one of its most pressing challenges: the development of a skilled and competent workforce to support the transition to Open Science. Through its core objective of unifying and enhancing training and capacity-building initiatives across Europe, Skills4EOSC directly contributed to the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda¹ and aligned with the evolving priorities of the EOSC Partnership and EOSC Association.

The project’s efforts were anchored in building a collaborative and sustainable **network of Competence Centres**, fostering a coherent approach to skills development and knowledge exchange. A major contribution to this goal was the **Skills4EOSC Recognition and Accreditation Framework**, which harmonised the validation of training outcomes through the use of Open Badges and European Digital Credentials. This framework ensured quality and credibility, promoted the uptake and

¹ The **Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)** is updated whenever a new Multi-Annual Roadmap is produced. Currently, **SRIA 1.3** is undergoing its third revision.

recognition of Open Science training across institutions and communities in Europe.

Skills4EOSC established a formal liaison with the **EOSC Association** and the **EOSC Partnership**, ensuring alignment with key policy priorities and direct contributions to strategic documents such as the SRIA. The project actively participated in shaping the SRIA through key events and initiatives, including the EOSC Symposium (2023/2024), the Multi-Annual Roadmap 2023–2024 consultation (SRIA v1.1, November 2022), the Horizon Europe EOSC Development Working Group, and the EOSC Winter School (2024/2025) through the contribution to Opportunity Area 5 (Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition & Upskilling). These efforts were reflected in subsequent SRIA updates (v1.2, 2023 and v1.3, 2024), which explicitly referenced Skills4EOSC and recognised the importance of Competence Centres (model promoted by the project) and prioritised skills as a foundational element for a federated, sustainable EOSC.

In 2024, the **EOSC Federation² Handbook** was published to support EOSC’s operational phase. It served as a practical guide for organisations aiming to contribute to the EOSC Federation by creating or joining EOSC Nodes. Chapter 5 of the Handbook (items 5.1 and 5.4) encouraged the establishment of Competence Centres, which were encouraged to join the Competence Centre Network established under the Skills4EOSC Project.

This strategic alignment underscored Skills4EOSC’s strategic role in supporting EOSC's broader vision: a trusted federation of services and infrastructures that enabled open and data-intensive research, with skills development and capacity building at its core.

² The [EOSC Federation](#) is a distributed network of independently managed "EOSC Nodes." These nodes collaborate to provide European researchers with access to a wide range of data, resources, and services. The federation aims to create a unified environment for open science by connecting various research infrastructures and making them interoperable through a common framework of standards and policies.

3.5 Cooperation with related EOSC projects and beyond

During the final year of the project, Skills4EOSC significantly expanded its collaboration with related EOSC projects and complementary initiatives across Europe. These efforts, documented in detail in the *MS8.4 Report on Cooperation with Related EOSC Projects and the EOSC Partnership*, were led under Task 8.2 and focused on aligning training activities, promoting Open Science and FAIR principles, and enabling reuse of skills-related outputs across the broader EOSC ecosystem.

A total of nine major collaborations with EU-funded projects were documented, including **FAIR-IMPACT, EuroScienceGateway, OSCARS, CLARIN, COALESCE, ATRIUM, TETRIS, CATALISI, and EOSC Beyond**. These partnerships took the form of:

- Joint training initiatives, particularly on FAIR-by-Design methodologies and MVS-based curricula;
- Shared participation in key events such as the EOSC Symposium 2024 and the 2025 EOSC Projects Coordination Meeting;
- Co-development of strategic tools, such as the CLARIN Trainers' Toolkit and COALESCE's alignment on science communication strategies;
- Signed Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) with projects like COALESCE and CATALISI to formalise future collaboration and sustainability pathways.

Through these activities, Skills4EOSC helped strengthen the integration of Open Science training efforts across Europe, ensure alignment with EOSC policy and technical developments, and support a federated network of Competence Centres. In particular, Skills4EOSC role in co-developing and promoting the Competence Centre model has been reinforced by its visibility and contributions across these partnerships.

The project also engaged beyond the EOSC project landscape, establishing impactful collaborations with organisations such as **Ghent University** and the **Flemish Research Data Network (FRDN)**. These engagements allowed Skills4EOSC to reach wider institutional audiences and promote uptake of its outputs, such as the FAIR-by-Design methodology, at the national level.

A live “Overview of Collaborations” spreadsheet was maintained throughout the period, capturing cross-project activities, responsible contacts, and planned follow-ups, ensuring transparency and reusability of collaboration records within the consortium.

These synergies directly contributed to the project’s KPIs related to coordination and engagement, including surpassing the targeted number of established project and programme-level collaborations, and ensuring participation from over five European countries. Collectively, these cooperation efforts have amplified Skills4EOSC impact and set the foundation for continued collaboration and interoperability within and beyond the EOSC ecosystem.

3.6 Summary of the Key Performance Indicators

Channel	Activity	KPI Measure	Results
Project website	Information about outcomes and news	# of visitors	1,150 monthly average visits (2024-2025)
Social media channels	Information about outcomes and news	# of followers	LinkedIn: ~1,000; X: ~800
Online consultations	Surveys on MVSs, FAIR-by-Design methodologies	# of participants	154 participants total
Training pilots	Training and co-design workshops	# of events	8 pilot training initiatives
Training courses	Train-the-Trainer courses	# of courses and participants	72 courses, 896 registered users
Skills4EOSC Webinars	Webinar series and workshops	# of webinars/workshops	18 events organized
Participation in external events	Promoting project outcomes	# of events	13+ external events
Skills4EOSC Final Conference	Final dissemination event	# of participants	100+ participants
Zenodo	Open access	# of downloads	>8,000

repository	deliverables and materials		cumulative downloads
Learning platform	Digital learning ecosystem	# of badges issued	959 badges issued to learners
Learning platform	Assessment and engagement	# of assessment questions	4,670 questions completed
Competence Centres Network	Sustainable network building	# of active centres	11 active Competence Centres
Competence Centres	Mapping and engagement	# of mapped centres	26 Competence Centres mapped
Data Stewardship Networks	Professional network development	# of national networks	4 national DSN networks established
Open Science Communities	Community building	# of new communities	37 new OSC communities launched
Fellowship Programme	Professional development	# of fellows supported	9 data professionals supported
User Support Network	Technical support infrastructure	# of support channels	8 User Support Channels
Social media engagement	Community interaction	LinkedIn impressions	25,614 impressions (2024-2025)
Learning resources	Educational content	# of learning materials	308 distinct learning materials
Forum engagement	Community discussion	# of forum posts	277 posts in learning platform forums
Collaboration agreements	Strategic partnerships	# of formal partnerships	9+ MoUs and collaboration agreements

4 Communication and Dissemination Activities

Skills4EOSC dissemination strategy has included a wide spectrum of coordinated actions, including the organisation of events, participation in international fora, national-level experimentation, and the production of dedicated communication resources. These activities have contributed to raising awareness, building community capacity, and supporting sustainability pathways for project outcomes.

4.1 Online Communication Channels and Tools

The Skills4EOSC project has strategically invested in a suite of online communication tools to ensure wide visibility, accessibility and engagement across its diverse target audiences. These tools have played a critical role in disseminating project results, enabling reuse, and sustaining an open dialogue with the broader EOSC and Open Science community. This section outlines the main channels employed and how they have been used to amplify the project's key messages and outcomes.

4.1.1 Project website – structure, content strategy, analytics

The **project website** (www.skills4eosc.eu) is the cornerstone of the project's digital presence and acts as a central hub for all public-facing content. Its structure is designed for intuitive navigation, with six primary sections:

- **About** (overview, consortium, funding info),
- **Key Exploitable Results** (KERs),
- **News** (project updates and stories),
- **Resources** (deliverables, publications, visuals, presentations),
- **Network** (Competence Centres and stakeholder involvement),
- **Participate** (calls, events, feedback channels).

The **content strategy** prioritises clarity, accessibility and thematic organisation. For example, resources are grouped by type and purpose (booklets, deliverables, advocacy kits, infographics), while all entries include

direct download links and clear attributions. Language is adapted to suit non-expert stakeholders, and colour-coded banners allow for quick recognition of content categories aligned with the project’s visual identity.

The **analytics and performance monitoring**, managed by the WP8.6 lead (GARR), show that traffic to the site increases sharply during dissemination campaigns (e.g., the release of the Competence Centre Kit in June 2025 or final conference materials in July). User interactions, such as downloads and page views, are tracked and evaluated to refine communication efforts.

The Skills4EOsc website has recorded extraordinary growth over the three-year period analysed. Beginning with a monthly average of 204 visits during 2022-2023, the platform experienced its first significant surge in the following year, reaching 514 monthly visits on average. This upward trajectory accelerated dramatically in 2024-2025, with the monthly average climbing to 1,150 visits, marking an additional 124% growth compared to 2023-2024.

Content is regularly updated to ensure the site reflects the current status of outputs and events. The website is licensed under CC-BY 4.0, encouraging reuse.

4.1.2 Social media – X, LinkedIn, community engagement, metrics

Over the three-year period, Skills4EOsc has strengthened its presence across its social media channels:

- **X (formerly Twitter):** used for quick, real-time communication, the promotion of events, and networking activities;
- **LinkedIn:** the primary channel for raising awareness about the project, promoting events, dissemination materials (guidelines, booklets, deliverables), training opportunities (Skills4EOsc Training Courses), and webinars.

The analysis of Skills4EOsc's LinkedIn activity from September 2022 to August 2025 highlights steady and significant growth across all key performance indicators, confirming both the consolidation of the project’s digital presence and the effectiveness of the communication strategy adopted.

In particular, LinkedIn recorded a significant increase in user engagement and followers between March and June 2025, corresponding with targeted campaigns such as:

- the promotion of project support materials (guidelines, deliverables, booklets), launched in March 2025;
- communications related to the Skills4EOSC Final Conference, which generated high-impact content in terms of visibility, interest, and community interaction on the platform

The growing interest in social channels is also reflected in the continuous rise in follower numbers: LinkedIn is approaching the 1,000-follower milestone, while X is nearing 800. All performance indicators show a marked improvement: while the total number of LinkedIn impressions in 2022–2023 was approximately 5,850, this figure rose to 25,614 in the following two years (2024–2025). In addition to impressions, user interaction on LinkedIn increased significantly, both in terms of content reach and reactions.

Collaboration with EPOS.eu and the EOSC Association played a key role in the dissemination of content and networking efforts.

4.1.3 Zenodo community – open access to deliverables, training materials and publications

The **Skills4EOSC Zenodo community** (zenodo.org/communities/skills4eosc) serves as the official repository for the project’s open outputs. It hosts:

- Peer-reviewed project **deliverables** with DOIs,
- The full **Booklet Series**, designed for reuse in training and policy contexts,
- **Curricula materials**, templates and Quality Assurance Frameworks,
- **Multimedia content**, including final conference presentations and training videos.

Each resource is uploaded with full metadata, CC-BY 4.0 licensing, and clear attribution of authorship and funding. Deliverables are often published in parallel to the website to maximise discoverability.

This repository facilitates:

- Reusability of outputs across training and institutional contexts;
- Citation and traceability via persistent DOIs;
- Integration with other Open Science repositories and EOSC catalogues.

As of July 2025, over 50 entries are available, with cumulative downloads and views exceeding 8,000.

4.1.4 Video content and other media outreach

Video content has been a growing dimension of the Skills4EOSC outreach strategy, supporting both training and awareness-raising objectives. Types of video materials produced include:

- Tutorials (e.g. on FAIR-by-Design and MVS profiles),
- Webinar recordings from Skills4EOSC-led and co-organised events,
- Institutional interviews with Competence Centres and trainers,
- Highlights from major events, such as the final conference in Paris.

Videos are published on both YouTube and Zenodo, as well as embedded in the “Videos” section of the website. Efforts have been made to include subtitles and accessible formatting where possible. These materials are widely used in follow-up dissemination and as part of the Train-the-Trainer initiatives.

In addition to videos, the project has made effective use of:

- Infographics, diagrams and visual explainers integrated into booklets and policy briefs;
- Templates and slide decks for workshops and presentations;
- Email newsletters, reaching targeted mailing lists on a quarterly basis.

4.1.5 Use of EOSC/OS communities and forums for amplifying project visibility

Skills4EOSC actively participates in broader **EOSC and Open Science forums**, leveraging shared platforms and communities to expand its outreach beyond its own network. Engagement includes:

- **EOSC Association:** participation in task forces and inclusion in the official EOSC Project Catalogue (eosc.eu);
- **EOSC-related events:** Skills4EOSC has featured prominently at events such as OSFAIR, EOSC Winter Schools, and coordination meetings with related Horizon projects;
- **Partnerships with Open Science advocates:** including CATALISI, COALESCE, OpenAIRE, GO FAIR, and RDA, to co-develop content, contribute to webinars, and align policy messages;
- **Contribution to the future European Skills Academy** roadmap and working groups;
- **Cross-project clustering activities**, where deliverables (e.g., MVS and recognition frameworks) are shared for potential uptake by other initiatives.

This approach strengthens Skills4EOSC positioning within the EOSC ecosystem, reinforces the credibility of its outputs, and ensures that

dissemination efforts are not isolated but embedded in shared European infrastructures.

4.2 Events organised – conferences, workshops, webinars

Skills4EOSC has led and co-organised several high-profile events, aimed at engaging stakeholders in dialogue, training and policy exchange. The following highlights the most significant initiatives held between July 2024 and August 2025:

- **Science4Policy Workshop – Bridging the Gap between Research and Decision-Making** (Rome, 30-31 January 2025): This hands-on event empowered researchers to navigate science-policy interfaces using Open Science methods. With strong participation from national policy actors, it included live role-play sessions simulating decision-making processes.
- **Competence Centres Workshops:**
 - **Building a Sustainable Future for Open Science: Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Workshop** (Paris, 10 June 2025): This workshop, organised as part of the Skills4EOSC Final Event, brought together project partners and members of the emerging Competence Centre Network to discuss governance, support models, and the roadmap beyond the project lifecycle.
 - **Workshop: Making the Competence Centres Network Sustainable and Enhanced** (Berlin, 21 October 2024): This workshop, organised as part of the EOSC Symposium 2024, presented the updated Competence Centre Kit and facilitated structured discussions about long-term sustainability strategies.
- **FAIR-by-Design Trainings:**
 - **Making Learning Materials FAIR: An Introductory Guide to the FAIR-by-Design Methodology** (Online, 26 August 2025). An online webinar organised in collaboration with the Greek CC aiming to introduce the FAIR-by-Design Methodology practices to the Open Science Community in Greece.
 - **FAIR-by-Design Methodology Training for the FDRN Knowledge Hub** (Online, 20 May 2025). The online webinar provided best

- practices and practical advice on how to design FAIR learning materials to the Flemish research data management community.
- **FAIR-by-Design Methodology for Learning Materials** (Online, 25 April 2025). A general introduction to the methodology for the RDA in Norway group, focusing on practices and challenges related to the specific national and regional setting.
- **Making Training Materials Matter: Introducing the FAIR-by-Design Methodology** (Online, 14 & 21 March 2025). A two sessions train-the-trainer workshop delivered in collaboration with the ATRIUM Project, focusing on integrating FAIR principles into training content following the FAIR-by-design methodology developed in Skills4EOSC.
- **FAIR-by-Design Methodology for learning materials for CoP** (Online, 18 December 2024). The methodology was introduced to the OpenAIRE established Community of Practice that brings together trainers and instructional designers from different Open Science communities.
- **FAIR-by-Design Methodology in Training Development** (Online, 20 & 26 September 2024): Co-organised with CLARIN-IT, this train-the-trainers series introduced methods for embedding FAIR principles into educational content, focusing on metadata, quality control and sustainability.
- **Minimum Viable Skills Profiles: Implementation Using FAIR Signposting** (Online, 2 July 2024): Organised jointly with FAIR-IMPACT, this session introduced approaches to machine-readable MVS profiles for automated discovery.
- **National Use Case Workshops:**
 - **Germany - “Fostering Open Science: Skills, Profiles, and Learning Paths for a Collaborative Future”** (Online, 23 May 2025), an interactive 2-hour webinar designed for all stakeholders engaged in Open Science.
 - **Italy - “How Research Data Transforms Public Policymaking”** (Online, 20 May 2025): Co-organised with ICDI, this webinar

- showcased practical approaches to evidence-informed policy using Open Science tools.
 - **Austria - “The Importance of Scientific Collections and Open Science Competencies in Austria”** (Online, 8 April 2025): Addressed curators and RDM professionals managing open scientific collections.
 - **Finland - Webinar organised by the CSC RDM Competence Center** to give an overview of the training materials developed in Skills4EOSC (Online, 26 August 2025). The target audience (43 participants) was trainers in open science and research data management at Finnish research organisations.
- **Final Conference: “Building Capacity for Open Science”** (Paris, 11 June 2025): Hosted by Campus Condorcet and CNRS, this event gathered over 100 participants on-site and remotely. It featured the launch of the Competence Centre Kit, Quality Compass, and Booklet Series, and marked the culmination of three years of work. Further details are available in Section 4.5 below.

4.3 Participation in external events

In addition to its own events, Skills4EOSC has actively contributed to numerous international and thematic conferences:

- **EOSC Project Coordinators Meeting** (Brussels, 26-27 June 2025): This annual event brings together representatives from projects funded under Horizon Europe that contribute to the development and implementation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). With 33 projects participating, the 2025 meeting marks an important moment of exchange and alignment across the EOSC landscape.
- **First EPOS Summer School on geoscience data and Open Science** (Olot, 23-27 June 2025): a comprehensive and hands-on journey through RDM topics tailored to the geoscience community.
- **NFDI4DS/QUADRIGA/DiscoRSE hackathon on metadata for training materials** (Cologne, 23-25 June 2025): The practical aspects of implementing the FAIR-by-Design methodology, specifically metadata and

metadata schemas were discussed at the hackathon where the main goal was identifying common grounds across the different training/learning platforms and metadata approaches.

- **SAM Conference 2025** (Vienna, May 2025): Skills4EOSC’s materials were awarded for visual clarity and accessibility, helping the project build cross-sectoral connections in the science-advice-to-policy domain.
- **FAIR-IMPACT National Roadshow in Italy** (Genoa, April 2025): to present the activities of the Italian Competence Centre for Open Science (ICDI), which is currently under development, introduce the network of Competence Centres established within the Skills4EOSC project and highlight the training opportunities and courses developed to support Open Science practices across Europe.
- **IDCC25 – 19th International Digital Curation Conference** (Edinburgh, February 2025): The project hosted a dedicated workshop on sustainable training infrastructures, drawing interest from RDM communities globally.
- **ORBIT Workshop and Winter School** (Sofia, February 2025): Representatives delivered sessions on Open Science competencies and discussed recognition and policy alignment with early-career researchers.
- **3rd Open Science Symposium in Greece** (Athens, November 2024): Skills4EOSC presented progress on the FAIR-by-Design methodology and its application to national capacity-building efforts.
- **FAIR-IMPACT National Roadshow in Romania (online, October 2024)**: the participants were introduced to the main activities and outputs of the Skills4EOSC project with the main focus put on the FAIR-by-Design methodology, quality assurance, certification and training possibilities.
- **European Civil Protection Forum** (Brussels, June 2024): Project representatives highlighted the use of open data in policymaking, including lessons from the Science4Policy Kit.

4.4 Materials developed – flyers, posters, policy briefs, slide decks

The project has invested significantly in high-quality, modular and visually unified dissemination products, including:

- **Flyers and posters:** featured at EO SC Project Coordinators Meeting, SAM 2025, EO SC Symposium, and IDCC25, aligned with the colour-coded Skills4EO SC identity and thematically tailored;
- **Slide decks:** developed for trainers and speakers, using branded templates in multiple formats (PowerPoint, OnlyOffice);
- **Policy briefs and Booklets:** condensed, shareable versions of key deliverables, including those on FAIR-by-Design, MVS, Science4Policy, and Honest Brokering;
- **Event recordings:** hosted on Zenodo and YouTube, include edited webinars, training sessions and conference highlights;
- **Visual kits:** infographics, icon sets and template elements reused across events and publications.

These materials contributed not only to knowledge transfer, but also to broader awareness of Open Science culture and Skills4EO SC strategic outcomes.

Skills4EO SC Leaflet, poster, etc.

<p>LECTURE 01 Open Science values and principles</p> <p>Training Course 1: Open Science is the new norm Module 01: Fundamentals of Open Science</p>	<p>LECTURE 02 FAIR Principles and their role in Open Science</p> <p>Training Course 1: Open Science is the new norm Module 01: Fundamentals of Open Science</p>	<p>LECTURE 01 Societal and Economic impact of Citizen Science from Galileo to post-truth populism</p> <p>Training Course 1: Open Science is the new norm Module 02: Open Science and Society</p>
<p>LECTURE 02 Societal Impact of Open Science - Real-life examples</p> <p>Training Course 1: Open Science is the new norm Module 02: Open Science and Society</p>	<p>LECTURE 01 Open Science: Benefits for scientific progress</p> <p>Training Course 1: Open Science is the new norm Module 03: Open Science is Essential for Advancing Research and Innovation</p>	<p>LECTURE 02 Open Science in Practice (optional)</p> <p>Training Course 1: Open Science is the new norm Module 03: Open Science is Essential for Advancing Research and Innovation</p>

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SCIENCE4POLICY AREA

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www.skills4eosc.eu |

Skills4EOSC Science4Policy training & resources for researchers and policy-makers

Skills4EOSC is an international consortium tasked with developing training and other resources to support Open Science and help make the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) a reality. Science for Policy interacts with Open Science in key ways, as reflected in the 6 project outputs below.

EVIDENCE-INFORMED DECISION MAKING (EIDM) LEARNING PATH

- Train-the-Trainer format
- Open Science, research integrity, communication & collaboration, ethical & legal issues, impact & challenges, policies and practices
- 7 online courses with recorded lectures, self-assessment quizzes & additional resources
- Self-paced and free to reuse

SCIENCE4POLICY WORKSHOP

- 2 days, in person
- Led by experts
- Fundamentals of effective science communication and science-informed decision making
- Theory and hands-on practice
- Building community and collaboration across disciplines and sectors

SCIENCE4POLICY INITIATIVE KIT FOR COMPETENCE CENTRES

- 10 Initiative types with descriptions
- Created via landscape analysis and survey of stakeholders
- Real-life, successful examples of initiatives from across Europe
- Good practices and practical advice for design & implementation

ETHICAL, LEGAL AND SOCIAL IMPLICATIONS (ELSI) FOR POLICY

- A practical handbook for civil servants and policy makers, to help them collaborate with researchers and integrate Open Science practices into their work
- Covers personal data protection, Intellectual property rights, and ethics in research and Open Science, including FAIR data principles

GUIDELINES FOR HONEST BROKERS

- Honest Brokers act as neutral intermediaries, facilitating the use of scientific evidence in decision-making without pushing a particular agenda
- Guidelines and best practices for Honest Brokers operating within the Open Science ecosystem

OPEN COLLECTIONS

- Offers policy-makers insight into the essential connections between the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Open Science, and Open Collections across various domains, including relevant use cases

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS / We want to gratefully acknowledge the important contributions of all Skills4EOSC WP3 Participants, EIDM training course authors and instructors, and Science4Policy workshop organizers and instructors.

Skills for the European
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Commons

Empowering Open Science

ACCESS A VALUABLE RESOURCE OF KNOWLEDGE AND TOOLS THROUGH OUR COMPREHENSIVE TRAINING AND STRONG NETWORK OF COMPETENCE CENTRES

www.skills4eosc.eu

Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Registry & Competence Centre Network

Competence Centres are pivotal for advancing expertise in specific domains like Open Science and FAIR data. They serve as central hubs, offering resources, training, and best practices. For prospective centres, joining this network provides recognition, collaboration opportunities, and amplifies their impact within the expert community.

Setting up a Competence Centre

Join a CCs Network

Project Partners
The Skills4EOSC consortium comprises a diverse group of 44 organizations from 18 Member States and Associated Countries, including universities, research institutions, and national and regional bodies.

This fact sheet provides a comprehensive overview of the Skills4EOSC project, its objectives, and its expected impact on the Open Science landscape. Skills4EOSC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101059272 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee (grant number 104043).

Skills4EOSC Training Courses Info & How to Register

Skills4EOSC provides a comprehensive training program for researchers, data stewards, and stakeholders to navigate Open Science and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Utilizing a Train-the-Trainer model, certified trainers are recognized as Master Trainers, ensuring consistent, high-quality training delivery.

General Courses | **Science4Policy** | Open Science Ready Institutions | Thematic Open Science

Skills4EOSC Publications Skills4EOSC Zenodo community

Skills for the European Open Science commons: creating a training ecosystem for Open and FAIR science.

Skills for the European
Open Science
Commons

ELEVATE OPEN SCIENCE SKILLS!

Through a unified training ecosystem a pan-European initiative to cultivate open and FAIR science skills for researchers and professionals.

Once Master Trainers are equipped with adequate competencies, they will organize courses to train target roles in their country/community.

Addressing Critical Gaps in Open Science Competencies

Skills4EOSC directly tackles the three key gaps identified in the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA):

1. FILLING THE OPEN SCIENCE AND DATA EXPERTISE GAP

By developing harmonized curricula and integrating Open Science essentials into academic programs, Skills4EOSC is helping build a strong foundation of Open Science knowledge.

2. DEFINING DATA PROFESSIONAL PROFILES AND CAREER PATHS

The project is mapping career profiles and defining Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS) to provide clear pathways for Open Science professionals.

3. OVERCOMING FRAGMENTATION IN TRAINING RESOURCES

Skills4EOSC is creating a FAIR by Design methodology for learning materials and establishing a network of Competence Centres to foster collaboration and resource sharing.

Open Science Competency Development

OS Gaps	Key outcomes	Researchers	Research Support Staff	Trainers & Mentors	Policy-makers & Leaders	Institutions / Providers
1^o Filling the Open Science & Data Expertise Gap	<p>Harmonized Curricula and Learning Paths Developing standardized Open Science (OS) training for researchers, data professionals, and policymakers across Europe.</p> <p>Train-the-Trainers (TtT) Courses Scaling-up the number of qualified OS trainers through effective training programs.</p> <p>Open Science 4 Policy Courses Delivering specialized training for researchers, policymakers, and civil servants to promote the use of OS in evidence-based policy.</p>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2^o Defining Data Professional Profiles and Career Paths	<p>Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS) Setting clear competence requirements for various Open Science roles to foster professional recognition.</p> <p>Professional Networks Building communities for data stewards, researchers, and other professionals to support continuous learning and exchange of best practices.</p>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
3^o Overcoming Fragmentation in Training Resources	<p>Competence Centre Network Establishing a coordinated network of national, regional, and thematic Competence Centres to provide support and harmonize training efforts.</p> <p>FAIR by Design Methodology Ensuring that training resources are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR), maximizing their impact.</p>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

4.5 Skills4EOSC Final Conference

The final conference of the European project Skills4EOSC, held at Campus Condorcet in Paris on 11 June 2025, brought together key stakeholders to reflect on the achievements of the project and outline future steps for building Open Science capacity across Europe.

The event, titled **“Building Capacity for Open Science”**, featured representatives from the European Commission, national governments, research infrastructures, and training organisations. Discussions centred on the role of Competence Centres, the professionalisation of data stewardship, and the importance of harmonised and inclusive training.

Speakers highlighted the gap between European Open Science policy and everyday research practice. Only 20 percent of researchers currently apply FAIR principles, underscoring the urgent need for stronger support structures, practical training, and cross-border cooperation.

The conference showcased results from the Skills4EOSC project, including the mapping of 26 Competence Centres and the development of eight pilot training initiatives. The project’s approach to defining a “Minimum Viable Skillset” for Open Science was presented as a scalable model for future efforts.

A recurring theme was the need to embed Open Science competences in higher education curricula and to support early-career researchers through clear, accessible pathways. The role of national networks, interdisciplinary communities, and open educational resources was also emphasised.

In closing, the project’s coordinators called for the long-term sustainability of the networks and tools developed by Skills4EOSC, recognising that competence and collaboration are key to making Open Science a daily practice in European research.

Further information and the event recordings are available at <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/news/skills4eosc-final-conference-recordings-presentations-and-photos-now-available>.

Skills4EOOSC Final Conference

5 Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy

5.1 The Co-Creation Methodology

In the Skills4EOSC project, a structured co-creation methodology was adopted to ensure that the key outputs of Work Package 2 (WP2), particularly the Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS), reflect the real needs, practices, and feedback of the targeted stakeholder communities. The **co-creation process** was designed with a cyclical and participatory approach, structured in three main phases:

- 1. Preparation Phase** – Although not the focus of Task 2.6, this initial stage laid the groundwork by analysing existing documentation and conducting preliminary interviews. The goal was to align future outputs with the community's expectations from the outset.
- 2. Development Phase** – This phase involved the active co-creation of content, directly engaging relevant stakeholders in the drafting and design of project outputs. Stakeholder involvement ensured that the materials under development were rooted in actual roles, workflows, and skill needs.
- 3. Adjustment Phase** – The core of Task 2.6, this phase focused on the iterative refinement of the outputs, based on structured feedback gathered through questionnaires, interviews, and consultation workshops. Stakeholders were asked to evaluate early drafts and prototypes, identify strengths, highlight gaps, and assess the relevance of classifications and use-case scenarios (e.g., distinguishing between Embedded and Coordinating Data Stewards in the MVS structure).

To extend this approach beyond WP2, a feedback form and process were established for the project tasks piloting Train the Trainer (TtT) courses, built upon the co-creation methodology developed in Task 2.6. This process includes a post-mortem review of each pilot, gathering structured feedback from trainers and participants to support evidence-based improvement of future courses and materials.

Throughout this process, the project relied on continuous and reflexive feedback, enabling dynamic adjustments based on real-world input. The co-creation approach not only improved the quality and relevance of the final outputs but also fostered a stronger sense of ownership and alignment within the community.

Stakeholder data was collected in three key dimensions: (1) respondent profile and stakeholder group; (2) context of professional engagement with Open Science, FAIR practices, and related skillsets; and (3) direct feedback on the project outputs. This structured data collection informed subsequent refinements and supported a more targeted and inclusive finalisation of WP2 deliverables.

5.1.1 FAIR-by-Design methodological approach

The FAIR-by-Design Methodology, developed under Skills4EOSC WP2, Task 3, integrates FAIR-specific actions into a six-stage backward instructional design model, spanning ideation to publication and verification. The six-stage methodology itself incorporates a culture of continuous improvement. This approach ensures that both new and existing learning resources can be aligned with FAIR principles over time.

Embracing continuous improvement from the project start, the methodology has been shaped through a structured co-creation process that actively engaged a wide range of stakeholders: project partners, external practitioners, and thematic communities. The objective has been to ensure the methodology is grounded in practical experience, adaptable to diverse contexts, and enriched by multiple perspectives.

The co-creation process began after the development of the initial draft of the FAIR-by-Design Deliverable, which based on a thorough review of instructional design best practices and FAIR principles. This early version was shared with all Skills4EOSC partners, accompanied by a project-wide webinar to present the methodology, gather questions, and invite suggestions for refinement. Feedback from this first round was consolidated into a revised draft, which was then published on Zenodo together with an EC survey form aiming to gather broader community input. This input was then used to develop the final version of the FAIR-by-Design Methodology deliverable. However, even this version of the methodology is continuously considered as a living document. To ensure inclusivity and openness, the T2.3 team established **multiple channels for continuous feedback** and participation:

- **Surveys:** A continuously open EC survey for the methodology itself together with feedback forms in the FAIR-by-Design Training of Trainers (ToT) course and other training events enable any interested party to provide feedback at any time.
- **Workshops and Trainings:** Structured discussion collection at the end of each event, both internal and external have also proven to be very effective as participants shared experiences or asked questions that helped further develop the methodology.
- **Public Repositories:** All methodology materials are hosted on GitHub where discussion forums, issue tracking, forks, and pull requests enabling direct community contributions.
- **Postmortem Documents:** A specific postmortem template has been shared with the project training materials designers to be able to capture structured reflections from their experience, lessons learned and recommendations.
- **Direct Communication:** Email and meeting-based exchanges with T2.3 have been used to actively help methodology practitioners and get their direct opinion and quality of experience on different methodology stages.

The feedback gathered through these channels has directly informed enhancements to the methodology and its supporting resources. Some of the most important include:

- **Enhanced Multimedia Integration** – Detailed instructions for embedding videos and other media in FAIR-by-Design templates.
- **FAIR Signposting** – Collaboration with FAIR IMPACT to implement machine-readable metadata through Level 1 and Level 2 signposting, added to templates.
- **Tool-Agnostic Templates** – Open document format templates and a microlearning unit for adopters without GitHub/Markdown experience.
- **Interactive Navigation Map** – A clickable overview of methodology steps to guide users quickly to relevant content.
- **Guidance for Closed Materials** – Clear protocols for publishing full metadata while restricting access to content when necessary.
- **Reuse Training** – Workshops with practical examples on licensing, attribution, and integrating existing materials.

With this approach the co-creation process extended well beyond the project consortium, bringing in perspectives from various domains such as CLARIN, ATRIUM, and RDA. WP3 and WP4 within Skills4EOSC also applied the methodology to develop materials for policymakers and structured learning paths, contributing substantial feedback through their postmortem documentation. Across all engagements, open discussions at the end of training sessions emerged as a key source of actionable insights, often surfacing practical challenges and context-specific needs.

As a direct result of co-creation, several new resources have been published in the Skills4EOSC Zenodo Community:

- **MS2.4 Final Recommendations on FAIR-by-Design Training Resources** that consolidates best practices and lessons learned.
- **Short Guidebook** that provides a concise, user-friendly reference outlining the main actions in each methodology phase.
- Implementation Success Stories such as the **DoRANuM case**, illustrating adaptability and real-world impact.
- **Community Case Reports** that provide detailed documentation of the adoption processes, challenges, and solutions, such as those from CLARIN-ERIC.

The FAIR-by-Design co-creation process has intentionally been designed as an ongoing, open-ended cycle. The technical infrastructure supports transparent versioning and release notes, allowing users to track changes. Open contribution channels, combined with regular stakeholder engagements, have ensured that the methodology continues to evolve, integrating new insights, addressing emerging needs, and strengthening its role as a practical, adaptable framework for producing FAIR learning materials.

5.1.2 Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS)

The development of the Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVSs) in Skills4EOSC followed a structured co-creation methodology involving six iterative steps: defining the use case, describing the role and Open Science (OS) mission, identifying essential skills, selecting relevant controlled vocabulary terms, using the MVS to inform learning outcomes, and reviewing the results with trainers and stakeholders. This process was repeated across drafts, enabling continuous refinement of each profile. Both internal and external contributors, including training designers, domain experts, and members of the target roles, were engaged to validate the relevance and applicability of the MVSs. The approach was flexible and adaptable, allowing profiles to be shaped by literature review, practical feedback, and community consultation.

This collaborative process led to the definition of **14 role-specific MVSs** covering a broad range of Open Science actors, such as Data Stewards, Researchers, Policy Makers, Civil Servants, Knowledge Brokers, Digital

Collections Curators, and Scholarly Communication Professionals³. An initial public consultation via EU Survey in March 2023 gathered 11 expert contributions, which helped prioritise key roles. In April 2024, a co-creation workshop in Vienna involving the Austrian GLAM community attracted 91 participants from 35 institutions, directly informing the development of the MVS for Digital Collections Curator.

A second round of **public review in April 2025** collected 54 responses from 16 countries, confirming the relevance of the MVSs and their potential for adoption. Most respondents indicated that the profiles reflected the skills needed for practising Open Science and were suitable for reuse in their organisations.

Training pilots were also instrumental in validating and improving the MVSs. The undergraduate student MVS was updated after pilot delivery, which revealed gaps in topics such as intellectual property, open licensing, and research impact. A full learning path for evidence-informed decision-making was designed using MVSs for policy makers, civil servants, and knowledge brokers, aligning course objectives with essential Open Science competencies.

Finally, the CSC Competence Centre in Finland successfully used the Data Steward MVS in a teaching context at the University of Tampere. Students reviewed the profile, discussed required skills, and reflected on how these could be developed through work experience—demonstrating the profile’s effectiveness as both a training and engagement tool.

The Data Steward curriculum was also presented and discussed during the Orbit Winter School on February 5, 2025, in Sofia, Bulgaria. Lessons were delivered to 14 young data stewards, providing an opportunity to present the curriculum and collect feedback.

This comprehensive co-creation approach ensured that the MVSs are not only aligned with FAIR and OS principles, but also practical, adaptable, and

³ Detailed information is available in D2.6 Catalogue of OS career profiles and MVS - update <https://zenodo.org/records/15731870>

ready to be reused and localised by Competence Centres, training providers, and institutions across Europe.

5.1.3 Co-creation activities for the Science4Policy (EIDM Learning path)

The Train-the-Trainer learning path on “Open Science and Evidence informed decision making” (EIDM) in WP3 was developed through a collaborative process that engaged a broad range of stakeholders involved in Open Science and decision making, including domain experts, experienced trainers and members of such communities, as the final target audience for this learning path were policy makers, civil servants and knowledge brokers. A key design element for this learning path was the alignment with the Minimum Viable Skillsets for these three profiles and the FAIR-by-design methodology.

During the delivery phase, **pilot TtT trainings were implemented**, gathering important insights for successive improvements to both the training curriculum and the delivery process. Round 1 of the final TtT trainings also generated valuable insights that led to updates in the activities and structure of Round 2. Further feedback from round 2 was again used to inform the final content, that was translated in self-paced-only courses.

Finally, in parallel, **national pilot trainings** were conducted from trainers in 15 participating countries. These trainers adapted the core materials to their local policy environments and institutional needs, and immediate feedback from these events was also taken into account, for future suggested activities.

More details on the methodology and results from the training design and delivery of the EIDM learning path can be found in the D3.2 Evidence-based policy and Public Administration training final report, that will be published by August 31, 2025.

5.1.4 Pilots and feedback on professional and thematic learning paths

WP4 dedicated two tasks (4.1 and 4.2) to create professional learning paths for data stewards and other data professionals detailed in Deliverable 4.24. These curricula targeted specific Open Science new professional roles and their development following a competency-based approach, involving iterative consultation with domain experts, trainers, and members of the professional communities concerned. Three specific learning paths were piloted (open licensing, reproducible research, and ethical-legal-social issues (ELSI)) across partner institutions. The feedback received in the **co-creative process of these pilots** validated both the content and the instructional design, and allowed the refinement of the learning objectives and training materials to ensure that curricula are context-aware and ready for reuse by training providers, Competence Centres and also Higher Education Institutions willing to train these newborn professions.

The main objective of WP5 is to support the development of skills and capacities among professionals working in Research Infrastructures and researchers in four disciplinary areas: Social Sciences and Humanities, Climate Change, Solid Earth Sciences, and Digital Collections.

WP5 developed sets of training modules and learning paths tailored to each discipline. The learning paths serve as step-by-step guides designed to meet the needs of different professional profiles within each thematic field, as identified in the Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS). Each path is aligned with clear learning objectives and adapted to the specific context of the discipline.

The relevance and effectiveness of the learning paths and training materials were assessed through pilot training events and Train-the-Trainers sessions.

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/15691090>

These sessions also aimed to establish a network of individuals and Competence Centres to sustain training activities within each field.

To ensure that both discipline-specific perspectives and the activities of Competence Centres were well integrated into the learning paths, WP5 followed an iterative design process. This included regular consultations with the relevant communities and Competence Centre representatives.

Following the pilot training events, an in-person workshop was organised to identify areas for improvement. Competence Centres presented their Open Science training activities and provided feedback on the current versions of the learning paths and training modules, informing collective action planning and discussions on future collaboration.

Additional feedback collected after the Train-the-Trainers sessions was integrated to the final WP5 report (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16992361>), which presents recommendations for delivering training both across thematic communities and within each disciplinary area.

5.2 Coordination with national and European initiatives and networks

Throughout the project, Skills4EOSC ensured strong coordination with both national and European initiatives. This was achieved through active participation in key strategic events and by establishing the Competence Centres Network (CCNet).

At the European level, coordination activities included high-level meetings such as the **EOSC Association Winter Schools** (2024 and 2025), where Skills4EOSC contributed to **Opportunity Area 5** (Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition & Upskilling), as well as participation in coordination meetings hosted by the European Commission.

A major result of this coordination effort was the inclusion of Skills4EOSC and its Competence Centres Network in two key EOSC documents published in 2024:

- the EOSC Federation Handbook (see paragraph 3.4)
- the EOSC Implementation Roadmap, which includes many important results from the project.

At national level, both project partners and members of the Competence Centres Network played a vital role by organising and participating in many **strategic national workshops, Tripartite events, and other activities** involving research institutions, infrastructures, and policy makers.

In addition to event participation, Competence Centres coordinated local engagement by involving experts and master trainers from universities and research organisations in co-creation and training activities. They also helped disseminate the project’s main results using the Kit for Competence Centres, making it easier to promote adoption and reuse of the project’s outputs.

These figures demonstrate how the national dissemination efforts of the Competence Centres translated into active participation in the project's training offer. The strong representation from countries with active Competence Centres also suggests that local engagement strategies, co-creation activities, and the use of the Skills4EOSC Kit have been effective in attracting and supporting diverse research communities across Europe.

The creation of the **Competence Centres Network** is one of the project's key coordination achievements. Since its public launch in June 2023, the network has brought together national Competence Centres to share practices, align strategies, and co-develop sustainable support structures for Open Science training and skills development.

The coordination activities included **six thematic online workshops** on governance, sustainability, and training, culminating in the **General Assembly** and coordination workshop held in Paris at the final conference in June 2025.

Based on these discussions, the Competence Centres Network is seen as both a collaboration forum and an enabler, providing national CCs with access to shared tools and knowledge. There was broad agreement that the network should remain community-driven, take a grassroots approach, and not attempt to duplicate existing structures (such as RDA) or become a top-down governing body that overrides national or regional autonomy.

One of the key messages that clearly emerged from the network's activities was: "Placing the Human Factor at the Core of EOSC." This means that a sustainable EOSC must prioritise people. Researchers, data stewards, and institutional staff need to be at the centre of Open Science policies and practices to ensure long-term success. Competence Centres, with their mission to support training and upskilling for Open Science, are ideally positioned to connect researchers with the services and resources that will be provided by the emerging EOSC Nodes.

Competence Centres also play an essential role in harmonising curricula, training and knowledge sharing across Europe. Using a shared methodology based on MVS and FAIR-by-Design approach can help ensure consistent skills

development and facilitate collaboration. Looking forward, the creation of an EOSC Knowledge Hub or Academy could further strengthen these efforts and provide long-term support for Open Science capacity building.

Alongside the Competence Centres Network, another key channel for coordination and impact has been the development of professional networks. **Four national Data Stewardship Networks (DSNs)** were established during the project, each closely linked to their respective Competence Centres and supported strategically by Skills4EOSC.

Data Steward Networks

Network	Launch	Membership	Support/Affiliation
Italy CIDS	November 2023	172	Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure
Hungary HDSN	October 2024	40	Not yet established
Portugal PDSN	March 2025	70	Re.Data with Foundation for Science & Technology (FCT-FCCN)
Nordic Countries NDSN	July 2025	> 300	Nordic e-Infrastructure Collaboration (NeIC)

Supporting Funded by the European Union UK Research and Innovation

As an example, the Italian Data Stewardship Network, known as the Comunità Italiana dei Data Stewards (CIDS), is a bottom-up initiative supported by the Italian Competence Centre ICDI and Skills4EOSC. The project contributed to its design and launch, helped organise a national survey, promoted the network to new members, and provided resources such as the Network Starter Kit. Thanks to international connections and strategic mentoring, CIDS has grown into a model for peer-led knowledge exchange and professional development.

In Portugal, the national network Rede Portuguesa de Data Stewards (RPDS) was co-developed by Skills4EOSC and a group of national stakeholders. The

project team initiated and facilitated regular coordination meetings, provided mentoring and strategic direction, and ensured alignment with national efforts. Tools, templates, and cross-network exchanges were shared, and the network is now embedded in the Re.Data initiative and supported by FCT FCCN.

The **Hungarian Data Stewardship Network**, Magyar Adatgazdász Hálózat (MAH), was established through close collaboration between Skills4EOSC and local stakeholders. The project supported early engagement, provided regular mentoring and strategic advice, facilitated community building and knowledge sharing, and ensured connection with the Hungarian Competence Centre. MAH is now exploring pathways for formalisation and long-term sustainability.

The **Nordic Data Stewardship Network** (NDSN) represents a supranational effort involving stakeholders from all five Nordic countries. Skills4EOSC played a central role in designing the network, facilitating the development of its governance and strategic planning, and supporting monthly coordination meetings. A Steering Group was formally established in May 2025, and the network is now associated with the Nordic e-Infrastructure Collaboration (NeIC), ensuring continuity and regional alignment.

To support alignment and collaboration across these national networks, Skills4EOSC also contributed to the international level. Project members co- led the creation of Task Group 7 (TG7) under the RDA Professionalising Data Stewardship Interest Group. TG7 provides a global forum for data stewardship networks to share tools, practices, and experiences. The group connects initiatives from Europe (including all Skills4EOSC-supported DSNs), North America, and Latin America, and offers a sustainable space for knowledge exchange and continued collaboration beyond the end of the project.

Other important initiatives with strong impact, which received substantial support from Skills4EOOSC and contributed to coordination efforts at both national and European levels, further strengthened the project's reach and sustainability.

A key development was the establishment of **Open Science Communities (OSCs)** across Europe. These are inclusive, peer-led learning communities that promote the uptake of Open Science practices by connecting researchers, encouraging exchange, and making everyday workflows visible and reproducible. Through four editions of the international OSC Incubator Programme, Skills4EOOSC trained 45 participants and supported the launch of 37 new communities, involving nearly 200 members. These OSCs now serve as local hubs for engagement, connecting researchers with institutional stakeholders and helping to foster a culture of Open Science.

Iteration	Duration IP	# participants started	# founded OSCs	# members
1	March – June, 2023	11	6	65
2	January – April 2024	9	8	110
3	September – December 2024	13	13	13
4	January – May 2025	12	10	4

Details per iteration of the OSC Incubator Program

Overview of newly founded OSCs for each of the iterations of the OSC Incubator Program

Skills4EOSC also played a key role in supporting thematic networks in domains where FAIR principles are still developing. In the area of artificial intelligence, a collaborative study on FAIR data practices gathered input from 67 experts across 15 countries thanks to a consultation with global experts through the RDA FAIR4ML (machine learning) IG. The process resulted in a community-endorsed list of 10 recommended practices, providing a concrete basis for future work and stimulating further international discussion on reproducibility and interoperability in AI research.

In the field of health technology, Skills4EOSC worked to identify needs and initiate a network focused on FAIR practices in prosthetics design. Although the resulting group did not formally become an RDA Interest Group, it helped connect researchers across disciplines, generated practical recommendations, and built bridges with existing networks, including the **SciLifeLab Metadata Network in Sweden**.

Skills4EOSC also supported the development of a network for data curators in museums and heritage collections. Led by the Natural History Museum Vienna, the initiative engaged stakeholders nationally and internationally, established a Steering Board and launched communication activities. The Skills4EOSC Train-the-Trainers course brought together 65 participants from museums, universities, and libraries, creating momentum for the adoption of FAIR practices in object-based data curation and laying the groundwork for future collaboration within the museum and collections community.

Lastly, the **Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme** supported nine data professionals through 1–3 month secondments at 12 host institutions across Europe. The programme was implemented in two calls and targeted data professionals such as data stewards, librarians, and RDM specialists, in line with the Marie Skłodowska-Curie mobility rules. Fellows and host institutions were selected through an open call, and participants received financial support for travel and accommodation.

In total, four fellows were selected in the first call and five in the second. Fellows reported high satisfaction with the experience, highlighting the quality of the hosting teams, exposure to diverse RDM practices, and new professional development opportunities. Hosts appreciated the fresh perspectives and tangible contributions brought by the fellows. Several hosts expressed interest in sustaining long-term collaborations beyond the project.

Tangible outputs from the fellowships included technical prototypes, DMP templates, metadata course designs, training materials, and new collaborations—some of which led to co-authored publications.

As an example, this article describes the experience of a fellow hosted at the Technical Institute of Denmark, offering valuable insights into the mutual benefits of the programme.

All these initiatives demonstrate the broader impact of Skills4EOSC beyond its core structures. By enabling new communities, thematic networks, and professional development opportunities, the project created strong links between individuals, institutions, and national strategies—laying the

foundation for lasting coordination and progress in the European Open Science landscape.

5.3 Competence Centres Network and Sustainability of Results

The Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Network represents the project's primary vehicle for ensuring long-term sustainability and exploitation of results. Established as a lightweight organization based on in-kind contributions, the network currently comprises eleven active Competence Centres across Italy, Greece, Finland, Sweden, North Macedonia, France, Luxembourg, Poland, Germany, Czech Republic and Spain with several additional institutions expressing interest in joining. The network operates under a formal governance structure including a **General Assembly** and Presidency, supported by collaborative frameworks through Memoranda of Understanding (MoU) and Letters of Intent (LoI) that facilitate knowledge exchange, training delivery, and best practice sharing. New Competence Centres can join by signing a LoI expressing their alignment with the network's mission, later formalizing participation through an MoU once their engagement is consolidated.

The network's operational framework includes provisions for establishing Working Groups focused on specific tasks and an **Editorial Board** responsible for managing the evolution of best practices, standards, and potentially overseeing an Open Science Skills Journal. On July 24th, the network held its first General Assembly and elected Sara Di Giorgio, the Skills4EOSC project coordinator representing the Italian Competence Centre ICDI, as President. This appointment ensures continuity between the project phase and the network's autonomous operation. Under her leadership, the network has committed to expanding membership by actively engaging new Competence Centres and launching calls among network members to activate the Editorial Board and establish new Working Groups based on emerging community needs.⁵

⁵ More details are available in the D7.3 Report on CCs and user support networks and

Complementing the Competence Centres Network, the **User Support Network** (USN) has been established to facilitate the adoption of open science practices across research infrastructures and computing centres. The USN brings together eight User Support Channels from diverse institutions across Europe, providing technical, operational, and consultancy support to researchers. Since its formal launch in September 2024 with a kick-off meeting attended by 40 participants from 24 institutions, the USN has organized regular meetings and maintained active communication through dedicated services including a repository, Mattermost channel, and mailing list to foster knowledge sharing and collaborative projects among member organizations.

The network's commitment to adopting and evolving Skills4EOSC methodologies, particularly the Minimum Viable Skillsets and FAIR-by-Design approaches, ensures continued value creation for the European Open Science community. With established technical infrastructure, shared service portfolios, and strategic alignment with EOSC Federation objectives, the Competence Centres Network provides a robust foundation for maximizing the long-term impact and exploitation potential of all project outcomes across Europe and beyond.

recommendations for networks evolution <https://zenodo.org/records/15262091>

5.4 Training and Support to Master Trainers

The **Skills4EOSC learning platform**, accessible at <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/>, represents a significant Key Exploitable Result that demonstrates substantial engagement and scalability within the European research and education community.

The platform has successfully established itself as a comprehensive digital learning ecosystem with 72 curated courses specifically designed to address the evolving skills requirements in the European Open Science Cloud domain, offering both synchronous and asynchronous learning modalities to accommodate diverse learner preferences and scheduling constraints. With a registered user base of 896 individuals and 3,117 role assignments across various learning contexts, the platform has achieved considerable reach within its target demographic of researchers, data scientists, and EOSC stakeholders. The engagement metrics reveal a robust learning environment where users actively participate through 277 forum posts and interact with 4,670 assessment questions, indicating meaningful pedagogical engagement rather than passive consumption. The platform's educational resources comprise 308 distinct learning materials complemented by a sophisticated recognition system featuring 55 unique badges, of which 959 have been issued to learners, demonstrating successful completion and skill acquisition pathways. The average course participation of 48.60 learners per course suggests sustained engagement and effective knowledge transfer mechanisms. Each course contains an average of 22.34 modules, reflecting comprehensive curriculum design that supports progressive skill development.

This learning infrastructure represents a key exploitable asset that can be leveraged beyond the project lifecycle through institutional partnerships, integration with existing European education frameworks, and expansion into adjacent research domains. The platform's demonstrated capacity to attract and retain users while facilitating measurable learning outcomes positions it as a scalable solution for addressing the persistent skills gap in digital research competencies across Europe.

- Number of courses (72)
- Number of users (896)
- Number of role assignments (3117)
- Number of posts (277)
- Number of questions (4670)
- Number of resources (308)
- Number of badges (55)
- Number of issued badges (959)
- Average number of participants (48.60)
- Average number of course modules (22.34)

To support the dissemination of training courses, particularly within the Competence Centre network, a promotional leaflet was produced, listing all course dates and registration details, along with a series of visual mockups designed to advertise each course on social media channels.

Skills4EOSC Training Courses / Overview

COURSE AREA	TITLE OF THE COURSE	WHERE
GENERAL	IMPLEMENTING FAIR-BY-DESIGN METHODOLOGY (FAIR) (YET ANOTHER INTRODUCTORY COURSE ON OPEN SCIENCE)	COURSE
SCIENCE&POLICY	OPEN SCIENCE IS THE NEW NORM	COURSE
	ELSI AND DATA GOVERNANCE	COURSE
	INTRODUCTION TO EVIDENCE-INFORMED DECISION-MAKING	COURSE
	OPEN SCIENCE STAKEHOLDERS AND COLLABORATION STRATEGIES	COURSE
	EMPOWERING THE FUTURE OF RESEARCH WITH OPEN SCIENCE	COURSE
OPEN SCIENCE READY INSTITUTIONS	OPEN SCIENCE POLICIES SUPPORT OPEN SCIENCE PRACTICES	COURSE
	IMPLEMENTING OPEN SCIENCE POLICIES	COURSE
	OPEN LICENCES FOR DATA SOFTWARE AND CODE	3 RD ROUND / 2 ND ROUND
	LEARNING PATH FOR ELSI PROFESSIONALS: ELSI PERSPECTIVES IN OPEN SCIENCE	3 RD ROUND / 2 ND ROUND
	LEARNING PATH FOR (DATA) LIBRARIANS: TECHNICAL SKILLS ARE THE BRIDGE TO REPRODUCIBLE RESEARCH	COURSE
THematic OPEN SCIENCE	TEACHING OPEN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT FOR UNDERGRADUATES	COURSE
	SHAPING OPEN SCIENCE CHAMPIONS: A TRAIN-THE-TRAINERS COURSE FOR EDUCATORS OF PhD CANDIDATES	COURSE
	DATA MANAGEMENT FOR RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE (RI) PROFESSIONALS	COURSE
	DATA MANAGEMENT FOR RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE (RI) PROFESSIONALS	COURSE
	DATA MANAGEMENT FOR RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE (RI) PROFESSIONALS	COURSE

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Open Science and Evidence-informed Decision Making Training Courses

Introduction

The Skills4EOSC project offers 7 innovative open and reusable training courses, designed to equip policymakers, civil servants, and honest brokers with the skills to adopt Open Science and make evidence-based decisions. Running from October to December 2024, these courses are part of a comprehensive training programme developed by the project to empower researchers, data professionals, policymakers, and other stakeholders in Open Science and FAIR data management practices.

Each course offers:

- 2-3 hours of self-paced learning;
- 2-hour live session;
- Self-paced materials available one week before each live session;
- Get ready for active participation: review training materials to make the most of the live session.

Overview of the courses

COURSE 1	COURSE 2
Open Science is the New Norm Explore the transition to Open Science, its fundamental principles, and societal impact. Learn how Open Science fosters collaboration and transparency.	Ethical, Legal, and Societal Implications (ELSI) and Data Governance Understand the ethical and legal frameworks of Open Science, focusing on data governance and FAIR principles within the EU.
Level: Beginner	Level: Beginner
Date: 18 th October 2024, 10:00 AM - 12:00 PM CET	Date: 23 rd October 2024, 10:00 AM - 12:00 PM CET
Certification: Badge "Fundamentals on Open Science"	Certification: Badge "ELSI and Data Governance"

The high number of participants was made possible thanks to the active promotional efforts carried out by individual Competence Centres through their national and local networks. This demonstrated the project's actual

scalability and capacity to reach a broad and diverse audience. The training offer was particularly well received, as it responded to a widespread demand for knowledge on Open Science practices, addressing multiple levels, from policy makers to researchers and contributing to the development of skills across roles and institutions.

5.5 National Use Cases – local engagement and exploitation pathways

Skills4EOSC has carried out targeted local engagement activities to pilot project outputs and promote grassroots uptake. These include:

- Webinar series in **Italy** with the ICDI Competence Centre, focused on training researchers and civil servants on linking data practices with policy needs;
- **Austria's** pilot programme for Open Science-aware curators, supporting data stewardship for cultural heritage collections;
- **Germany's** Competence Centre webinar (23 May 2025), focusing on adaptation of Skills4EOSC materials to institutional strategies.
- **North Macedonia's** Competence Centre workshop (17 June 2025) with the aim to introduce the Competence centre activities and mainly focus on the benefits of the Skills4EOSC project activities and main outcomes, specifically the membership in the CC network.

These national experiences provided valuable insights on localisation, institutional support models, and long-term sustainability of training networks.

5.6 Facilitating adoption and integration of project outcomes within and beyond the consortium

Skills4EOSC during its lifetime has built a pan-European network of Competence Centres (CCs) to ensure long-term sustainability and broad uptake of its outputs. These local and thematic CCs serve as hubs to deliver training, implement the Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) framework, apply the FAIR-by-Design methodology, and host Master Trainer courses and

e-learning modules. By aligning national centres through a coordination strategy tailored to local maturity levels, Skills4EOSC ensures widespread institutional embedding and federated adoption of its core training ecosystem.

In the context of WP8, Skills4EOSC has established formal partnerships—such as through a signed Memorandum of Understanding or Collaboration Agreement—with projects like NI4OS-Europe, FAIR-IMPACT, EOSC Focus, OSCARS, COLAESCE, ATRIUM and other EOSC related projects driving shared objectives around training and skills frameworks, achieving to expand its reach beyond the consortium. For example, the NI4OS-Europe partnership included commitments to share training materials, harmonize metadata schemas, and co-develop FAIR-by-Design methodologies and learning-path frameworks across Southeast Europe. Similarly, collaboration with FAIR-IMPACT focused on joint curriculum development, outreach coordination, and embedding FAIR principles into trainer practice, leveraging each project’s geographical and thematic coverage to maximize EOSC reach.

All types of collaborations with other projects, initiatives and organizations are monitored internally with the use of *Overview Project Collaborations*, a living document, stored in the project’s common workplace with open access to all members of consortium, as well as described in details in the relevant reports.

Skills4EOSC leveraged major EOSC-wide events to weave project outputs into the wider ecosystem. Participation to the EOSC Winter Schools and the annual EOSC Projects Coordination Meeting have enabled sharing of methodologies, materials, and strategic impact insights with other Horizon Europe projects. Last but not least, the final conference in Paris (June 11, 2025), co-organized with CNRS and the French Ministry of Research, showcased the project’s training frameworks and network impact while explicitly inviting further collaboration with EOSC Federation Nodes and other initiatives in Europe.